

Self-Modulated Adaptive Robotic Deposition (SMART DEPOSITION)

1 st Marco Maccarini SUPSI DTI, IDSIA Lugan, CH marco.maccarini@idsia.ch	2 rd Asad Ali Shahid SUPSI DTI, IDSIA Lugan, CH asadali.shahid@idsia.ch	3 rd Dario Piga SUPSI DTI, IDSIA Lugan, CH dario.piga@idsia.ch	4 nd Loris Roveda SUPSI DTI, IDSIA Lugan, CH loris.roveda@idsia.ch
---	--	---	---

Abstract—In modern industrial applications, the ability of robots to learn and adapt their motion is increasingly necessary. This is particularly true in tasks such as welding and material deposition, where the robot must plan and execute a path for a wide range of target scenarios. The current method of setting up these applications requires expert operators to manually generate a robot path for each part, which is a time-consuming process that can take at least one day to complete for each new part. In the case of deposition tasks, several activities must be carried out, including generating a deposition path in the CAD environment, converting the path into robot instructions, defining collisions-free robot motion, testing for quality assessment, and updating the path for desired deposition quality. To reduce setup time and standardize the task, there is a high demand for automating the path generation to achieve the desired quality.

This paper focuses on the automatic sealant deposition for the assembly of aerospace parts, which requires adapting the deposition path based on the target part geometry and material properties. The proposed Self-Modulated Adaptive Robotic Deposition (SMART DEPOSITION) tool offers a solution for generating and adapting robot motion in response to the deposition requirements of a target part. To accomplish this, the approach first analyzes the input part geometry to generate a grid of points. Then, an optimal deposition path is computed by exploiting the traveling salesman problem, using multiple approaches such as the nearest neighbor, a two-opt algorithm, and simulated annealing. The generated path can then be used to plan and execute the robot motion, resulting in the desired deposition quality with a standardized approach. The simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach in optimizing the deposition path for different parts with varying geometries.

Index Terms—intelligent robotics; Industry5.0; task optimization; autonomous robotics; path generation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Robots have become an essential component of modern manufacturing processes, especially in precisely controlled environments [1]. However, the current robot systems are not capable of handling the diversity and complexity of unstructured settings [2]–[4]. For instance, in industrial applications like sealing, welding, and painting, the robots need to adapt their motion continuously to meet changing task specifications [5], [6]. The conventional approach of defining each segment of the path that the robot needs to follow becomes inefficient for low-volume and high-variation manufacturing environments where

production demand can change drastically [7].

Recent studies have explored using vision systems to design flexible robotic cells for different manufacturing tasks like sealant dispensing and welding [8]–[10]. However, vision-based approaches rely on sophisticated hardware, which comes at a high computational cost and increased expenses. To overcome these challenges, the paper proposes the Self-Modulated Adaptive Robotic Deposition (SMART DEPOSITION) approach, a CAD-based adaptive path generation system for robotic sealing.

The SMART DEPOSITION approach takes the geometrical coordinates of the part extracted from the CAD file as input and generates the optimal path for sealant deposition while meeting the specified constraints. The approach optimizes the deposition path through the traveling salesman problem using multiple algorithms like the nearest neighbor, a two-opt algorithm, and simulated annealing. The optimized path generated by the approach can be used to plan and execute the target deposition task with a standardized approach, achieving the desired quality.

The paper presents simulation results demonstrating the capabilities of the SMART DEPOSITION approach in optimizing the deposition path for different parts, showing its generalizability properties [4]. The proposed approach can significantly improve the efficiency and quality of robotic sealing tasks in low-volume and high-variation manufacturing environments, reducing costs and improving productivity.

II. METHODOLOGY

This section quickly describes the SMART DEPOSITION method used to solve the optimization problem related to the robot path generation for deposition tasks.

In order to be optimal, the deposition path must provide a complete and homogeneous spread of the material on the target part. To achieve this, the deposition lines should be correctly spaced to avoid overlaps while guaranteeing enough deposited material. In addition, the shortest path has to be computed to save time and material.

The procedure is composed of the following steps: *input image*, *points grid*, and *traveling salesman problem* optimization. *Input image* represents the part geometry on which the deposition task is performed, *Points grid* represents the

Identify applicable funding agency here. If none, delete this.

generation of points among the part geometry that will be used by the *Traveling salesman problem (TSP)* in order to create the optimal deposition path. In the following, each of these components is described.

A. Input image

The coordinate vector \mathbf{F} of the target part is used as an input to the system, which contains the coordinates of each node N ,

$$\mathbf{F} = [[N_{1_x}, N_{1_y}], [N_{2_x}, N_{2_y}], \dots, [N_{m_x}, N_{m_y}]], \quad (1)$$

where $[N_{i_x}, N_{i_y}]$ represents the x and y coordinates of a node i , while m is the total number of nodes in \mathbf{F} .

The part coordinate vector \mathbf{F} provides information about the part, *i.e.*, the length between nodes $d(N_i, N_j)$ and the total space occupied by the shape $min_x, min_y, max_x, max_y$:

$$d(N_i, N_j) = \sqrt{(N_{i_x} - N_{j_x})^2 + (N_{i_y} - N_{j_y})^2}, \quad (2)$$

$$min_x = \min_{\forall N \in \mathbf{F}} N_x \quad min_y = \min_{\forall N \in \mathbf{F}} N_y, \quad (3)$$

$$max_x = \max_{\forall N \in \mathbf{F}} N_x \quad max_y = \max_{\forall N \in \mathbf{F}} N_y. \quad (4)$$

The information in the input file is used to create an input image, later used by the algorithm for the optimization of the deposition path.

B. Points grid

In order to create a path that covers the whole geometrical shape, a grid of points \mathbf{G} , distributed over the entire space is generated.

Algorithm 1 shows the pseudo-code to generate grid \mathbf{G} . Method 'linspace(A, B, D)' in line 1 and 2 returns an array composed of a series of D numerical elements equally distributed between the two extremes (A, B). Each sealant

Algorithm 1 Grid point creation

- 1: $x \leftarrow \text{linspace}(min_x, max_x, c)$
 - 2: $y \leftarrow \text{linspace}(min_y, max_y, r)$
 - 3: $\mathbf{G} = \text{array}([(i, j) \text{ for } i \in x \text{ for } j \in y])$
 - 4: **return** \mathbf{G}
-

material has specific properties, *i.e.*, density, viscosity, and coverage range (the extent of material spread), that affect the quality of final deposition. Due to this reason, it is possible to specify the density of the points in \mathbf{G} , changing the number of rows r and columns c of it. The structure of \mathbf{G} is similar to the structure of F . In fact, \mathbf{G} contains the coordinates of each point generated by the combination of rows r and columns c , $\mathbf{G} = [[V_{1_x}, V_{1_y}], [V_{2_x}, V_{2_y}], \dots, [V_{r \cdot c_x}, V_{r \cdot c_y}]]$. The grid \mathbf{G} contains $r \cdot c$ points. To sum up, \mathbf{G} contains points uniformly distributed over the entire geometrical shape. This means that some of the points generated could be out of the figure, and for this reason, it is necessary to remove the extra points by making use of the Algorithm 2, where the method 'G.pop(V)' deletes the V node (outside the part) from \mathbf{G} .

Algorithm 2 Cleaning grid point

- 1: **for each** $V \in \mathbf{G}$ **do**
 - 2: **if** V not inside the shape **then**
 - 3: $\mathbf{G}.\text{pop}(V)$
 - 4: **return** \mathbf{G}
-

C. Travelling salesman problem (TSP)

Once the cleaned grid \mathbf{G} is computed, it is possible to proceed with the optimization of the deposition path. In order to have a homogeneous deposition, the path needs to cover each point $V \in \mathbf{G}$ once and only one time and must return to the starting point. In other words, the deposition path has to be a **Hamiltonian cycle**. As reported in the literature [11], a Hamiltonian cycle of an undirected graph is a cycle that contains each node exactly once. In addition, the deposition path needs to be the shortest possible in order to consume the minimum quantity of material. Indeed, this goal is the same of the **traveling salesman problem (TSP)** [12]. Given a complete undirected graph, $Gr = (V, E)$ with edge costs $c(e) \geq 0$, the goal of the traveling salesman problem is to compute a Hamiltonian cycle C of Gr of minimum cost:

$$c(C) = \sum_{\forall e \in C} c(e). \quad (5)$$

The points grid \mathbf{G} can be seen as a complete graph $Gr = (V, E)$ in which every pair of distinct vertices V is connected by a unique edge E .

III. RESULTS

Consider the convex part in Figure 1a as input to the SMART DEPOSITION tool. To generate a deposition path for this shape (Section II-B), it is necessary to generate a grid of points (Figure 1b), and to remove points outside it (Figure 1c). For this part, the points grid has been set with $c = 20$ and $r = 10$, with a total of $r \cdot c = 200$ points. After the cleaning, the grid contains 89 points. Once the cleaned grid is obtained, it is possible to generate the path using the TSP algorithm.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the SMART DEPOSITION tool, an approach for adaptive path generation and optimization (w.r.t. the part shape and the considered sealant material properties), has been proposed to plan and execute the robot motion to solve deposition tasks. Given the target part geometry CAD file as input, a grid of points is generated to compute the optimal path using the TSP approach. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed approach can generate the optimal path for different part geometries and sealant materials properties. Future work will be devoted to improving the computational efficiency of the algorithm. In addition, experimental tests are also foreseen making use of a Universal Robot UR10 within the H2020 CS2 ASSASSINN project.

Fig. 1: Complete example showing the steps for the optimization of the deposition path given the target part. First, the grid is defined and cleaned. Then, the path is created and optimized to satisfy the given constraints on overlaps and to be contained inside the part.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work has been developed within the project ASSASSINN, funded from H2020 CleanSky 2 under grant agreement n. 886977.

REFERENCES

[1] F. Vicentini, N. Pedrocchi, M. Beschi, M. Giussani, N. Iannacci, P. Magnoni, S. Pellegrinelli, L. Roveda, E. Villagrossi, M. Askarpour, et al., Piros: Cooperative, safe and reconfigurable robotic companion for cnc pallets load/unload stations, Bringing innovative robotic technologies from research labs to industrial end-users: the experience of the european robotics challenges (2020) 57–96.

[2] A. A. Shahid, J. S. V. Sestin, D. Pecioski, F. Braghin, D. Piga, L. Roveda, Decentralized multi-agent control of a manipulator in continuous task learning, *Applied Sciences* 11 (21) (2021) 10227.

[3] A. A. Shahid, D. Piga, F. Braghin, L. Roveda, Continuous control actions learning and adaptation for robotic manipulation through reinforcement learning, *Autonomous Robots* 46 (3) (2022) 483–498.

[4] L. Roveda, P. Veerappan, M. Maccarini, G. Bucca, A. Ajoudani, D. Piga, A human-centric framework for robotic task learning and optimization, *Journal of Manufacturing Systems* 67 (2023) 68–79.

[5] A. Gasparetto, P. Boscariol, A. Lanzutti, R. Vidoni, Path planning and trajectory planning algorithms: A general overview, *Motion and operation planning of robotic systems* (2015) 3–27.

[6] L. Roveda, B. Maggioni, E. Marescotti, A. A. Shahid, A. M. Zanchettin, A. Bemporad, D. Piga, Pairwise preferences-based optimization of a path-based velocity planner in robotic sealing tasks, *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 6 (4) (2021) 6632–6639.

[7] V. Kuts, T. Otto, T. Tähemaa, K. Bukhari, T. Pataraiia, Adaptive industrial robots using machine vision, in: *ASME International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition*, Vol. 52019, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2018, p. V002T02A093.

[8] P. Maiolino, R. Woolley, D. Branson, P. Benardos, A. Popov, S. Ratchev, Flexible robot sealant dispensing cell using rgb-d sensor and off-line programming, *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing* 48 (2017) 188–195.

[9] L. Yang, Y. Liu, J. Peng, Z. Liang, A novel system for off-line 3d seam extraction and path planning based on point cloud segmentation for arc welding robot, *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing* 64 (2020) 101929.

[10] P. Zhou, P. Zheng, J. Qi, C. Li, A. Duan, M. Xu, V. Wu, D. Navarro-Alarcon, Neural reactive path planning with riemannian motion policies for robotic silicone sealing, *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing* 81 (2023) 102518.

[11] P. Hell, H. Nishiyama, L. Stacho, [Hamiltonian cycles in covering graphs of trees](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dam.2020.03.013), *Discrete Applied Mathematics* 282 (2020) 271–281. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dam.2020.03.013>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0166218X20301050>

[12] M. Jünger, G. Reinelt, G. Rinaldi, The traveling salesman problem, *Handbooks in operations research and management science* 7 (1995) 225–330.